

The Portrayal of Indian Society in Untouchability Mulk Raj Anand

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Abstract

This study discusses the portrayal of the sufferings of the poor and oppressed in Mulkraj Anand's novel Untouchable. The sufferings of impoverished and complete trampled have been a familiar sight in India the ages. Poverty is exalted in theological terms, but in real life, the necessitous and the ended brace are looked kaput upon and ill-treated. His novel created a writer's revolution both in writing in Indian languages and sufferings of penurious and extinct crush. Anand has located the protagonist Bakha in an established reality in the hope of capturing the essence of the janitor's existence. One day action of the hero is intended to represent a relatively complete sociological experience.

Keywords: poor, cast-system, untouchable, humanism

Introduction

Indian English literature originated as a necessary outcome of the introduction of English education in India under colonial rule. In recent years it has attracted widespread interest both in India and abroad. They are richer in content and broader in range. In the 1930s 'Big three' of English Indian literature Mulk Raj Anand, Raja Rao and R.K. Narayan published their novels. His novels have no organic unity. His book almost reminds them of Joyce's Ulysses with its stream of consciousness technique.

Mulk Raj Anand was born on 12th December 1905 in Peshawar. He also studied and later lectured at League of Nations School of Intellectual Cooperation in Geneva. He is pre-independence fiction deals with several aspects of social reform, including the plight of the inviolable condition of the landless peasant in Coolie. His stories depicted a realistic and sympathetic portrait of the indigent in India. He was the first Indian novelist to make a sacrosanct the hero of a novel.

Untouchable is Anand's first novel and his most compact and artistically enough work. This novel represents one day in the life of 18-year-old Bakha, who are employed like dirt by all Hindus just because his profession is to clean restrooms. The next novel, coolie, has a broader canvas and is more diffuse in structure. Munro a young orphan works at a variety of odd jobs at Bombay, Daulatpur, and Simla till he dies at age 15 of tuberculosis caused on by undernourishment. Munro is exploited not because of his caste because he is needy. While Untouchable and Coolie are significant novels two leaves and

a bud is a dramatic novel about the difficulty of the laborers in a tea plantation in Assam; the book fails because Anand's approach is too simplistic; the English owners are shown as absolute villains. Anand has about seventy short stories to his credit published in six collections from time to time all his career.

Portrayal of Indian Society in Untouchable

The novel established Anand as one of India's leading English authors. The book was caused by his aunt's experience when she had a meal with a Muslim woman and was used as an outcast by his family. Anand's first turns around the argument for eradicating the caste system. It describes a day in the life of Bakha a young 'sweeper,' who is 'untouchable' due to his work cleaning latrines. Set in the fictional Indian town of Bulandshahr, The son of Lakha head of all of Bulashah's sweepers, Bakha is intelligent but naive, humble yet vain. As a crowd gathers around, Bakha pulls his sister away. Crying, she says to him that the priest sexually attacked her. A furious Bakha tries to go back to brave the priest, but an embarrassed and ashamed Sohini forces him to leave.

Back at home, it's only Sohini and Lakha. Rakha, Bakha's younger brother, is still out collecting food. Bakha tells his father that a high-caste man slapped him in the streets. Sensing his son's anger, Lakha tells him a story about the kindness of a high-caste doctor that once saved Bakha's life. This time Bakha runs towards town and ends up at the train station. Just as Bakha settles in to listen, Gandhi arrives and begins his speech. He talks about the plight of the outcast and how it is his life's mission to see them emancipated. This machine could mean the finish of untouchability. With this piece of hope, Bakha rushes home to share news of the Mahatma's speech with his father. At the time of this novel's publication, the caste system dominated India. In *Untouchable*, author Anand humanizes an "untouchable" human for his high-caste readers imploring them his description of Bahka and his family's suffering to consider the plight of their low-caste countrymen. This struggle was against British imperialism. The Indians were being treated like dogs. The wounds of Jalian wala bagh were not healed. The pattern of responses to the underdog emerges from the humanism of Anand.

The story of this prolonged indignity and humiliation of this class of society. Society belongs to the high castes. They are, in fact, the rulers and keep the low- caste as far away from them as they can. This novel revolves around Bakha, who is a libero boy. The author has taken a conspicuous day from his life and the presentation of the situation happening on that particular day he has drawn our attention towards the plight of low caste people. The first situation is the pollution touch of a caste Hindu. It creates a catastrophe. As Bakha walks along with the road eating 'Jalebi' and recalling the method he has made for learning English, his gaze is carried to a woman sitting in a window.

Bakha is seized with humility, fear, and servility. Of course, he was aware of his 'status' in life, but it was a sudden shock. This awareness of his status is "like a ray of light shooting darkness." The other significant situation in the novel is when Bakha's sister, Sohini, is molested by the priest. Thus they see that the holy men who appear in Anand's fiction are corrupt to the core and in their eyes; the lowest of low is quite touchable to satisfy their lust. For example, the ascetic in *Coolie*, he looks as Pandit Surajbhan in 'The Road' attracts a childless woman under the affection of turning her fertile. Here also the holy priest makes unsuccessful attempts to seduce Bakha's sister the author has exposed the contradiction in the thinking of the so-called high- caste people while a mere touch of the clothes of a hallowed is thought to pollute a more upper-caste sexual union is not- objectionable.

Bakha's world is much too narrow for his aspirations. So he longs for a new world. Anand, in the conclusion of *Untouchable* subtly examines the various possible solutions religious conversion

rapid industrialization and the Gandhian way. The emphasis on the Hutchinson's religion is on sin love and equality of birth whereas it is on cleanliness, morality, and dignity of work in Gandhi's approach to the problem of the emancipation of the castaways. Of these, Bakha likes only the idea of equality and cleanliness, but he feels become by Gandhi's sympathy.

It is only the third resolution offered by the poet Iqbal Nath Sarshar that engages Bakha's attention to the flush system. In the novel author creates a character who is seeking identity for himself in a world which has for ages suppressed his degrading social ill into which poets, philosophers, and reformers have fought over a thousand years. Anand's heroes are always living and improving with the present and struggling for the future.

Like postcolonial novels set in other parts of the British Empire, including Africa the main character's encounter with missionary Christianity produces comedy and satire. The book is concerned not with the life and sufferings of some particular individual but with the experience and pains of invincible as a class. The particularly Bakha the novelist has focused attention on the miserable plight of intangible generally. The novelist narrates a single-day event in the life of Bakha an eighteen years old boy. He is the son of Lakha the besom the cleaner of the restrooms. These two prominent characters, the author hammers active on the caste-conflict. Though this deadly disease of caste fight was on its summit before Independence, it is but seen much or less in almost every State of India. The leper or the socially separated people who form the most necessary part of a nation have to begin a deplorable and miserable life beyond explanation.

The novel depicts Bakha and his community's suffering realistically. They are forced to live in society excluded from the filthy locality. The theme of the story is very realistic. It is a graphic novel of socially damaged protagonist Bakha. It is a slice from a life without any modification. The novel begins with a realistic picture of the outcastes' colony. The book reveals a sensible and sensitive understanding of social exploitation inherent in the class and caste structure of colonial India and the ever-growing conflict between the forces of tradition and modernity in Indian society. Lakha characterizes the achieved trod invariants. Old age and sickness have given him lethargic, ill-tempered, and self-centered. He believed that the outcastes are born to serve others. He tolerates all social evils without a single word of complaint. He has obtained extreme servility as a consequence of a thousand years of racial and caste superiority that is in vogue in India.

The story of Bakha's illness reveals the virtuous features of a father. Once Bakha falls severely ill. Lakha rocks the child in his arm and blows a sleepless night. In the morning he rushes to Hakim Bhagwan Dass and begs to save the life of his son. Lakha realizes that his sin is beyond consideration and further implores to treat his child and to provide some medicine. The physician agrees and thus, Bakha is cured. Polygamy and Bigamy are common phenomena with the outcastes. But Lakha does not re-marry even after the death of his wife. He will be biased to his new wife and neglect his children. His reduction is an instinct.

Conclusion

Anand's humanism is the focal point of his fiction. He is a novelist of the underdogs a champion of the deprived almost as high as Dickens. The bottom dogs of the Indian society are heroes of his novels a sweeper, a coolie, a laborer, a villager but all they are human. He requires to eradicate these social problems by criticizing his books. It makes him a novelist of the lower class a lyricist of their sorrows and joy. His chief motive is to use the art for the amelioration of Indian underdog. Both Untouchable and Coolie deal with the social crimes of his own time, and he wants to eradicate these problems.

Anand was well familiar with the life of the expatriate boy Bakha has been modeled on one of his playmates. His novels exposed and satirized the hypocrisy, bigotry, and callousness of the

high caste Hindus whose can be polluted by the mere touch of a derelict like Bakha but whose like Pandit Kali Nath do not hesitate to molest an outcast girl Sohini.

The titles *Coolie* and *Untouchable* exhibits the motive of propaganda and the novels are absolute with purpose. Both of them are the tale human concern, a vehicle of humanism. The sociological interest of poverty, exploitation, and corruption are presented in *Coolie* and *Untouchable* with humanism as its focal credo. His incredible realism, his concern for humanity his insights into the lives of the Indian masses exposes his sensitive and perceptive mind his imagination, and his essential humanity.

Though most of his heroes are destitute suffering people, characters going to the middle class; upper class also issues, but they are the butt of his social satire. It is the underdogs- a Bakha and a Munoo- who have his sympathy on their side.

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